

HELICOBACTER PYLORI PREVALENCE AND ITS DETERMINANTS IN DISTRICT LAKKI MARWAT: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background: *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) is a significant human pathogen etiologically linked to chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, and gastric cancer. Despite its clinical importance, regional epidemiological data are essential for understanding local transmission dynamics. This study aimed to determine the prevalence and identify the demographic, clinical, and lifestyle correlates of *H. pylori* infection in the population of District Lakki Marwat, Pakistan.

Materials and Methods: An observational study was conducted from September 2024 to February 2025 among individuals presenting at gastroenterology outpatient departments of multi-centered hospitals. Data from 271 participants were collected, including blood samples for *H. pylori* serology and structured questionnaires covering demographic characteristics, health history, and lifestyle factors.

Results: The overall prevalence of *H. pylori* infection was 46.9%. Higher prevalence rates were observed in females (53.5%), individuals aged 20-35 years (39.4%), rural residents (75.6%), those with no formal education (29.9%), and housewives (41.7%). A statistically significant association ($p < 0.05$) was found between *H. pylori* infection and age ($p=.003$), education level ($p=.009$), and a clinical history of gastritis, peptic ulcer, or gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) ($p=.001$). A key modifiable risk factor was the practice of handwashing with water and soap, which showed a significant protective association ($p=.001$).

Conclusion: This study reveals a high prevalence of *H. pylori* infection in District Lakki Marwat, underscoring it as a major public health concern. The infection is significantly associated with specific demographic factors, pre-existing gastrointestinal conditions, and hygiene practices. These findings highlight the need for targeted public health interventions, including improved health education and sanitation, to curb the spread of *H. pylori* in this region.

INTRODUCTION

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) is a gram-negative, microaerophilic, spiral-shaped bacterium that colonizes the human stomach, particularly the antrum

(1). Despite its initial observation in the 19th century and subsequent findings linking spiral organisms to gastric pathology in the early 20th century, the

bacterium was largely neglected until its successful culture by Marshall and Warren in 1982, a discovery that revived global interest and established its pivotal role in gastroduodenal diseases (2). Today, *H. pylori* is recognized as a Class I carcinogen by the World Health Organization, being etiologically linked to chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease (PUD), gastric adenocarcinoma, and gastric mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue lymphoma (3).

The global prevalence of *H. pylori* infection is estimated at approximately 50%, but it exhibits significant geographic and socioeconomic disparities (4). Infection is less common in high-income countries (HICs) due to improved sanitation, living conditions, and socioeconomic status (5). In contrast, low and middle-income countries, including Pakistan, bear a disproportionately high burden of infection, with prevalence rates in adult populations ranging from 24% to 73% (6). This high prevalence is a major contributor to the incidence of gastroduodenal diseases in these regions (7).

The pathogenesis of *H. pylori* is mediated by an array of virulence factors that facilitate colonization and persistence in the harsh gastric environment. Key among these are urease, which neutralizes gastric acid by hydrolyzing urea to ammonia, and flagella, which provide the motility necessary to penetrate the gastric mucus layer (8). The bacterium exhibits high strain variability, and its interaction with the host triggers a robust inflammatory response that can lead to mucosal damage. More recently, outer membrane vesicles have been identified as crucial vehicles for delivering bacterial virulence factors, modulating host cell signaling, and influencing disease progression (4). Transmission of *H. pylori* occurs primarily via the fecal-oral and oral-oral routes, facilitated by the bacterium's detection in feces and dental plaque (8). Major risk factors include low socioeconomic status, overcrowding, unhygienic conditions, and consumption of contaminated water or food (9). Diagnosis can be achieved through both invasive methods, such as histology and rapid urease testing on gastric biopsies, and non-invasive methods, including serology, the urea breath test (UBT), and stool antigen tests (10). Serological tests that detect specific IgG antibodies are particularly useful for initial epidemiological screening due to their convenience and non-invasive nature (11).

In Pakistan, a country with a high prevalence of gastroduodenal diseases, regional studies are crucial to understanding the local epidemiology of *H. pylori* (12). District Lakki Marwat represents an understudied population where risk factors such as socioeconomic status, hygiene practices, and water sources may significantly influence infection dynamics. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the prevalence, demographic correlations, health history associations, and lifestyle risk factors of *H. pylori* infection among individuals visiting hospital Gastro OPDs in District Lakki Marwat. The findings will help to inform local public health strategies and control measures for this significant pathogen.

Materials and methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted from September 2024 to February 2025 in District Lakki Marwat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The study received ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board of Khyber Medical University Institute of Health Sciences, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants. A total of 271 participants were recruited through convenience sampling from gastroenterology outpatient departments of four multi-center hospitals. The sample size was calculated using RaoSoft software with a 90% confidence level and 5% margin of error.

Data collection involved administering structured questionnaires to gather information on demographic characteristics, medical history of gastrointestinal conditions, clinical symptoms, and lifestyle factors. Venous blood samples (2 mL) were collected from each participant and centrifuged to separate serum. *H. pylori* infection was detected using immunochromatographic test kits for anti-*H. pylori* IgG antibodies according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics software (Version 30). Data was coded and entered, and descriptive statistics were computed to determine frequencies and prevalence. Associations between *H. pylori* infection and demographic, clinical, and lifestyle variables were assessed using the Chi-square test, with a p-value of <0.05 considered statistically significant. The strength of significant

associations was further evaluated using Phi and Cramer's V tests, with values interpreted as follows: 0-0.1 (very weak), 0.1-0.3 (weak), 0.3-0.5 (moderate), and >0.5 (strong).

Results

Age-wise prevalence of H. pylori infection

By analyzing specific age groups in relation to the prevalence of H. pylori, the highest

prevalence rate (39.4%) was observed in the age group of 20-35 years. The second highly prevalent age group was 35-50 years, with a prevalence rate of 28.3% followed by other age groups. However, the lowest prevalence rate (6.3%) was found at an old age group of 65-80 years, as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1: Age-wise prevalence of H. pylori Infection.

Age in years	Positive Samples	Negative Samples	Total
05-20 (%)	17 (13.4%)	36 (25.0%)	53 (19.6%)
20-35 (%)	50 (39.4%)	62 (43.1%)	112 (41.3%)
35-50 (%)	36 (28.3%)	34 (23.6%)	70 (25.8%)
50-65 (%)	16 (12.6%)	12 (8.3%)	28 (10.3%)
65-80 (%)	8 (6.3%)	0 (0.0%)	8 (3.0%)
Total	127 (46.86)	144 (53.13)	271 (100%)

Education status-based prevalence of H. pylori infection

Among educational statuses, the highest prevalence rate (29.9%) was observed in individuals having no education. The lowest

prevalence rate was observed in individuals having higher secondary (8.7%) and university level (17%) education, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Educational status-based prevalence of H. pylori infection

Educational status	Positive Samples	Negative Samples	Total
Primary (%)	20 (15.7%)	26 (18.1%)	46 (17.0%)
Middle (%)	23 (18.1%)	28 (19.4%)	51 (18.8%)
Secondary (%)	18 (14.2%)	31 (21.5%)	49 (18.1%)
Higher secondary (%)	11 (8.7%)	26 (18.1%)	37 (13.7%)
University (%)	17 (13.4%)	11 (7.6%)	28 (10.3%)
No Education (%)	38 (29.9%)	22 (15.3%)	60 (22.1%)
Total	127 (46.86%)	144 (53.13%)	271 (100%)

Occupationally based distribution of H. pylori infection

A significant association between occupation and H. pylori prevalence was observed. The highest seropositivity rate was identified among

housewives (41.7%), followed by students (22.8%), with varying prevalence rates among other occupational groups (Table 3)

Table 3: Occupation-based distribution of H. pylori infection

Occupation of individuals	Positive Samples	Negative Samples	Total
Student (%)	29 (22.8%)	51 (35.4%)	80 (29.5%)
Housewife (%)	53 (41.7%)	41 (28.5%)	94 (34.7%)
Unemployed (%)	24 (18.9%)	24 (16.7%)	48 (17.7%)
Employed (%)	17 (13.4%)	26 (18.1%)	43 (15.9%)
Self-business (%)	4 (3.1%)	2 (1.4%)	6 (2.2%)
Total (%)	127 (46.86%)	144 (53.13%)	271 (100%)

Socio-economic status-based prevalence of H. pylori infection

Individuals belonging to various socio-economic statuses were analyzed for the prevalence of H. pylori infection. The highest prevalence rate was observed in the middle (63.8%) and lower class (29.9%), while the

lowest prevalence (6.3%) was observed in the upper class, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Socio-economic Status-based prevalence of H. pylori infection

Socio-economic status	Positive Samples	Negative Samples	Total
Lower class (%)	38 (29.9%)	44 (30.6%)	82 (30.3%)
Middle class (%)	81 (63.8%)	92 (63.9%)	173 (63.8%)
Upper class (%)	8 (6.3%)	8 (5.6%)	16 (5.9%)
Total (%)	127 (46.86%)	144 (53.13%)	271 (100%)

Commonly diagnosed symptoms of H. pylori infection

In the H. pylori-positive group, gastritis (91.3%) and stomach/duodenal ulcer (90.6%) were highly prevalent, with GERD also common (75.6%). Conversely, the H. pylori-negative

group presented with a significantly lower prevalence of these conditions, with GERD (53.5%) being the most frequent diagnosis (Table 5)

Table 5: Commonly diagnosed conditions in patients of H. pylori

Conditions	Positive Samples	Negative Samples	Total
Stomach or duodenal ulcer			
No	12 (9.4%)	133 (92.4%)	145 (53.5%)
Yes	115 (90.6%)	11 (7.6%)	126 (46.5%)
Total	127 (46.86%)	144 (53.13%)	271 (100%)
Gastritis			
No	11 (8.7%)	129 (89.6%)	140 (51.7%)
Yes	116 (88%)	115 (87.78%)	131 (48.3%)
Total	127 (46.86%)	144 (53.13%)	271 (100%)
GERDs			
No	31 (24.4%)	67 (46.5%)	98 (36.2%)
Yes	96 (75.6%)	77 (53.5%)	173 (63.8%)
Total	127 (46.86%)	144 (53.13%)	271 (100%)

Smoking, drinking water habits, and vegetarian status-based distribution

The analysis revealed significant associations between *H. pylori* infection prevalence and smoking habits, dietary patterns, and water source treatment. The prevalence of *H. pylori* was significantly higher among non-smokers

(87.4%) compared to smokers (12.6%). Contrary to the initial hypothesis, the prevalence of infection was significantly higher among individuals reporting a vegetarian diet (82.7%) than in non-vegetarians (17.3%), as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Smoking, Drinking Water Treatment, and Vegetarian status-based prevalence of *H. pylori* infection

Smoking Status	Positive Samples	Negative Samples	Total
No (%)	111 (87.4%)	127 (88.2%)	238 (87.8%)
Yes	16 (12.6%)	17 (11.8%)	33 (12.2%)
Total	127 (46.86%)	144 (53.13%)	271 (100%)
Vegetarian Status			
No	22 (17.3%)	23 (16.0%)	45 (16.6%)
Yes	105 (82.7%)	121 (84.0%)	226 (83.4%)
Total	127 (46.86%)	144 (53.13%)	271 (100%)
Drinking Water Treatment before consumption			
No	116 (91.3%)	130 (90.3%)	246 (90.8%)
Yes	11 (8.7%)	14 (9.7%)	25 (9.2%)
Total	127 (46.86%)	144 (53.13%)	271 (100%)

Washing of hands-based prevalence of *H. pylori* infection

The prevalence of *H. pylori* infection was analyzed relative to reported handwashing hygiene using soap and water. The highest prevalence (39.4%) was found among

individuals who reported rarely washing their hands. In contrast, lower prevalence rates were identified in those who reported often washing their hands (3.9%) and those who reported never doing so (9.4%) as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Washing of Hands based prevalence of *H. pylori* infection

Washing Hands with Water And Soap	Positive Samples	Negative Samples	Total
Always	20 (15.7%)	17 (11.8%)	37 (13.7%)
Often	5 (3.9%)	20 (13.9%)	25 9.2%
Sometimes	40 (31.5%)	69 (47.9%)	109 (40.2%)
Rarely	50 (39.4%)	27 (18.8%)	77 (28.4%)
Never	12 (9.4%)	11 (7.6%)	23 (8.5%)
Total	127 (46.86%)	144 (53.13%)	271 (100%)

Association of H. pylori infection with demographic information, health history, clinical symptoms, and lifestyle factors

Associations between H. pylori infection and demographic, clinical, and behavioral factors were assessed using the Chi-square test, with the strength of significant associations determined by Cramer's V.

Significant Demographic and Behavioral Associations

A statistically significant association was found between H. pylori infection and age (p = 0.003), educational level (p = 0.009), and handwashing frequency (p < 0.001). However, the strength of these associations was weak for age (Cramer's V = 0.241) and education (Cramer's V = 0.238), and moderate for handwashing frequency (Cramer's V = 0.291) shown in Table 8.

Clinical Associations

Strong and statistically significant associations were identified between H. pylori infection and both stomach/duodenal ulcers ($\chi^2(2, N=271) = 189.883, p < 0.001, \text{Cramer's } V = 0.837$) and gastritis ($\chi^2(1, N=271) = 176.957, p < 0.001, \text{Cramer's } V = 0.808$). In contrast, the association with GERDs was weak (Cramer's V = 0.250) as shown in Table 8.

Non-significant association

No statistically significant association was observed between H. pylori infection and occupation (p = 0.059), socio-economic status (p = 0.814), smoking (p = 0.842), vegetarian diet (p = 0.766), or water treatment practices (p = 0.763). The corresponding Cramer's values for these variables were negligible, indicating a very weak relationship ($V \leq 0.018$) shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Association of H. pylori infection with Demographic information, Health History, Clinical symptoms, and Lifestyle Factors.

Variables	Pearson chi-square V.	p-value	Phi-Value	Cramer's V value
Age	15.721 ^a	.003	.241	.241
Gender	2.592 ^a	.107	-.098	.098
Residence	1.884 ^a	.170	-.083	.083
Education	15.349 ^a	.009	.238	.238
Occupation	9.102 ^a	.059	.183	.183
Socio-economic status	.945 ^a	.814	.059	.059
Stomach/duodenal ulcer	189.883 ^a	.001	.837	.837
Gastritis	177.064 ^a	.001	.808	.808
GERD	16.998 ^a	.001	.250	.250
Loss of appetite	42.128 ^a	.001	-.394	.394
Smoking	.040 ^a	.842	-.012	.012
Vegetarian status	.089 ^a	.766	.018	.018
Source of drinking water	3.749 ^a	.290	.118	.118
Washing hands with water and soap	22.896 ^a	.001	.291	.291

Discussion

This cross-sectional study reveals a H. pylori infection prevalence of 46.9% among symptomatic individuals in District Lakki Marwat, Pakistan. This figure aligns

with the estimated global average but is characteristic of a developing region, situated between the high rates (80-90%) of low-income countries and the lower rates (<40%) of developed nations (13). The findings

underscore a significant public health burden and highlight several key demographics, clinical, and behavioral correlations of the infection.

Demographically, the prevalence was significantly higher among younger adults (20-35 years) and individuals with no formal education. The association with younger age contrasts with studies from Northwest Ethiopia that reported increasing prevalence with age (14), but mirrors patterns seen in other high-transmission settings where acquisition occurs early in life. The strong inverse relationship with education level ($p=0.009$) is consistent with global literature (15), likely mediated through limited health literacy and poorer adherence to hygienic practices. While higher prevalence was observed in females, rural residents, and housewives, these associations were not statistically significant, suggesting that underlying factors like socioeconomic status and hygiene may be more direct determinants than gender or residence alone.

Clinically, a robust and statistically significant association ($p=0.001$) was found between *H. pylori* infection and a prior diagnosis of gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, or GERD. This reaffirms the well-established pathogenic role of the bacterium in these gastroduodenal disorders. Regarding symptoms, while abdominal pain and bloating were common, they were not specific to *H. pylori* status. However, the infection was significantly associated with systemic symptoms like loss of appetite and weight loss, as well as frequent burping. The negative association with nausea and vomiting suggests that the symptomatic presentation of *H. pylori* is heterogeneous and may not reliably distinguish infected from non-infected individuals in a clinical setting, a finding supported by other studies (16).

Lifestyle factors provided critical insights into potential transmission routes. A highly significant association ($p=0.001$) was found with infrequent handwashing with soap, identifying poor personal hygiene as a major modifiable risk factor in this population (16). This aligns with the observed, though not statistically significant, trend of higher infection prevalence among individuals using well water as their primary source. The lack of a significant association with water source, contrary to some studies, but consistent with others (17), may be due to uniform contamination across different water sources in the

region or the dominant role of person-to-person transmission facilitated by poor hygiene.

Limitations and Conclusions

This study has limitations, including the use of a convenience sample from hospital OPDs, which may not be fully representative of the general population. Furthermore, serological testing (ICT) indicates past or present infection but cannot distinguish active from resolved cases.

In conclusion, the high prevalence of *H. pylori* in District Lakki Marwat is a considerable public health concern. The infection is significantly driven by modifiable factors, most prominently low education levels and poor hand hygiene. Public health interventions should therefore prioritize community-based health education programs focusing on improving sanitation and hygienic practices. Future research should employ longitudinal designs and more precise diagnostic tools to further elucidate causal pathways and evaluate the impact of targeted interventions.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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